

Federated vs. centralized learning for medical image classification and segmentation

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ABSTRACT

Deep learning (DL) has become an essential tool in medical imaging. However, privacy regulations often make it difficult to collect and share medical data, limiting the availability of large and diverse datasets needed to train robust models. Federated learning (FL) offers a solution by enabling collaborative model training across multiple institutions without compromising patient privacy. However, the impact of the number of clients and of unbalanced data distribution on model performance has received limited attention.

This study investigates the performance of FL compared to centralized learning (CL) in the tasks of medical image classification and segmentation under different client setups. For the classification task, we used chest X-ray (CXR) images to classify them into one of four categories using ResNet18. For the segmentation task, we used cardiac computed tomography (CT) images to train a 3D U-Net model to segment the left ventricle (LV) and the myocardium (Myo). For both tasks, we evaluated the efficacy of FL with 2, 4 and 8 clients with and without data unbalance, and an additional 16 clients setup for segmentation. In classification, the trained model achieved an accuracy of 0.93 in the centralized approach, with similar performance in federated settings. Performance remained consistent across balanced and unbalanced data distributions, with sensitivity consistently around 0.94. For segmentation, the centralized model yielded a Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) of 0.877 (Myo) and 0.926 (LV), and the FL approach models yielded a DSC of 0.867 (Myo) and 0.922 (LV); 0.867 (Myo) and 0.923 (LV); 0.863 (Myo) and 0.921 (LV) for 2, 4 and 8 clients respectively.

Our results show that FL achieves competitive performance compared to CL in medical image classification and segmentation tasks. Moreover, the experiments involving unbalanced data did not reveal any significant decrease in performance. For the segmentation task, the federated approach achieved consistent results for both structures across different client setups, closely matching the performance of the centralized model. These results suggest that FL is a viable alternative to CL, especially in scenarios where privacy and decentralization are important.

Keywords: Federated learning, medical image analysis, classification, segmentation, data privacy

1. INTRODUCTION

Data privacy and confidentiality are essential in the medical field to maintain trust between healthcare providers and patients, as well as in ensuring compliance with legal and ethical standards, and preventing unwanted access and misuse of private sensitive health information. The widely used CL scheme to train a neural network introduces security issues, especially with regard to data collection, since it requires to transmit those highly sensitive data to third parties. The FL approach to train neural networks addresses these issues by avoiding data sharing.¹

By transmitting models instead of data, FL offers a promising alternative in scenarios where sharing medical data across hospitals is restricted due to privacy concerns. It is a decentralized machine learning (ML) approach that enables multiple entities, such as hospitals, research centers, and scientists, to collaboratively train models without the need to share sensitive data.^{2,3} An FL architecture typically consists of a central server and several

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clients (entities involved in the training).² The central server acts as a coordinator of the training by initializing and distributing the model to the participating clients. Each of the clients then trains the model locally with its own data for a specified number of epochs, and then securely transmits the updated parameters of the model back to the central server where they are aggregated. This process of local training, parameter sharing, aggregation, and global model updating constitutes a single round in FL. The updated global model is then sent back to each client for the next round. In this context, the number of clients and the distribution of data between clients may be of primary importance, but have not been sufficiently studied.

The aim of this study is to evaluate the efficacy of a FL strategy in a variety of client setups, in comparison to that of a CL approach, in two different tasks: CXR classification and cardiac CT segmentation. It is conducted as a use case study within the framework of the European project PAROMA-MED,⁴ which aims to develop, validate and evaluate a platform-based hybrid-cloud delivery framework for privacy- and security-assured services and applications in federative cross-border environments.

2. RELATED WORK

In recent years, FL has gained considerable attention as an effective approach to address data privacy concerns in medical imaging applications. Several studies using DL have been considered for COVID-19 CXR classification and for cardiac CT segmentation.

FL has shown promising results in CXR classification, particularly for COVID-19 detection. Liu et al.⁵ explored FL by evaluating four network architectures: ResNet18, ResNeXt, COVID-Net, and MobileNet-v2. ResNet18 and ResNeXt have been shown to be the most effective models, with ResNet18 achieving the highest accuracy of 0.91. Similarly, Naz et al.⁶ compared centralized learning (CL) and FL approaches using models such as ResNet50, VGG16, and Inceptionv3. While CL achieved the highest accuracy of 0.98 (with ResNet50), FL demonstrated competitive performance, with only a marginal reduction of 4% in accuracy. These studies demonstrate the potential of FL to deliver robust performance, although minor decrease of accuracy may occur.

DL has also been widely used for heart segmentation on CT images, with various studies demonstrating its effectiveness in automating the delineation of heart structures.⁷⁻¹¹ Koo et al.⁸ aimed to evaluate the accuracy of a DL-based LV myocardium segmentation against 1000 manual delineations, achieving results comparable to manual methods with a Dice-Sørensen Similarity Coefficient (DSC) of 0.88 on 100 randomly selected cases. Similarly, Sharobeem et al.⁹ proposed a deep learning-based approach for whole heart segmentation on CT. Their method based on a Dense V-Net architecture achieved a DSC of 0.85 for the left ventricular cavity (LVC) and 0.93 for the left ventricular myocardium (LVM). Misonne et al.¹² extended these works by using FL with a 3D U-Net architecture for whole-heart segmentation. Their method achieved DSCs of 0.87 and 0.89 on the NSCLC and LCTSC datasets respectively, and a highest DSC of 0.94 on the Pediatric-CT-SEG dataset using federated averaging (FedAvg) as aggregation method.

While FL provides a promising solution for privacy protection, a major challenge arises from the distribution of data among clients. Specifically, when the training data across clients are not independent and identically distributed (non-IID), it can result in a decrease in performance.¹³ These challenges have been shown to have a negative impact on the convergence and generalization of FL models. Recent studies have explored the theoretical and empirical implications of these issues. For instance, FedAvg,¹⁴ one of the most widely used aggregation strategy, has been shown to suffer from slower convergence and higher update variance in case of non-IID data across clients due to data heterogeneity.¹⁵

3. MATERIALS & METHODS

3.1 Datasets

For the classification task, the COVID-19 Radiography Database^{16,17} was used. The dataset consists of 21,165 CXR images classified in four classes, namely (1) Covid-19 infection, (2) lung opacity, (3) normal (which corresponds to healthy cases) and (4) viral pneumonia. The dataset presents some imbalance between classes, which are distributed as follows: 3616 (17.08%) images for the "Covid-19" class, 6012 (28.41%) for the "lung opacity" class, 1345 (6.35%) for the "viral pneumonia" class and 10192 (48.15%) for the "normal" class.

For the segmentation task, data from two datasets has been used: the Multi-Modal Whole Heart Segmentation (MM-WHS) dataset¹⁸⁻²¹ and the dataset used to train the TotalSegmentator (TS) tool.²² The MM-WHS dataset provides 20 training CT cardiac images alongside the corresponding heart structure labels for each of them, and 40 unlabeled CT images for testing, from which 10 of them were manually delineated in order to be used as part of our test dataset. To obtain the relevant cardiac subset from the TS dataset, we filtered the 73 cases which are focused on the heart, or limited to the chest region. From those, 63 cases were used as part of the training set, and 10 were used as part of the testing set, resulting in a total training set of 83 images and in a total testing set of 20 images, when mixing the data from the two datasets together.

3.2 Preprocessing

For the classification task, the data has been preprocessed first by resizing the CXR images from 299×299 to 224×224 pixels using bilinear interpolation and then by applying min-max normalization to scale pixel intensities between 0 and 1. All the images were set to a pixel spacing of 1×1 mm.

Regarding the CT segmentation dataset, the study was focused on the segmentation of the myocardium (Myo) and the left ventricle (LV), the first step was to assign the same value to each of the structures, to ensure that each structure was not labelled differently between the two source datasets (MM-WHS & TS). Thus, the background voxel values were set to 0, the Myo voxel values were set to 1, and the LV voxel values were set to 2. The remaining structures were classified into the same class by assigning the voxel values to 3. Regarding the CT images, the preprocessing steps involved spatial and intensity standardization. The images were first oriented to the LAS (Left-Anterior-Superior) coordinate system and resampled to a isotropic voxel spacing of $1 \times 1 \times 1$ mm. As for the classification task, the intensities were normalized using min-max scaling. Finally, patches of $128 \times 128 \times 128$ voxel size were generated from the images and the corresponding masks, to be used as the input during the training. As with the CTs, the segmentation labels were oriented to the LAS coordinate system and resampled to a voxel spacing of $1 \times 1 \times 1$ mm.

3.3 Centralized and federated learning

To establish the baseline, a conventional centralized learning was first performed for each of the tasks. Subsequently, the federated approaches have been performed with 2, 4, 8 and 16 clients for the segmentation task, and with 2, 4, and 8 clients for the classification task.

For the classification task, the ResNet18²³ model has been chosen, which is widely used in classification tasks and has been shown to be effective for CXR classification.²⁴ During training, we used CrossEntropy as the loss function and a batch size of 4, 8 or 16 for 2, 4, and 8 clients, respectively. For the segmentation task, the 3D U-Net²⁵ architecture was used with an input batch size of 1. To train the model, the composite loss function of cross-entropy and Dice loss was used.

The aggregation method used was FedAvg, where the weights are averaged at the server and then transmitted to the clients at each FL round. To ensure consistent results between FL and CL, each FL round were limited to a single epoch for the local training. For both CXR image classification and cardiac structure segmentation, the federated averaging (FedAvg) strategy was used, where the weights from each client’s local model are averaged to create the global model after each round. In both of our experiments, Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) has been used as the optimizer, with the learning rate set to 10^{-3} . The model was trained for 65 epochs in CL and for 65 rounds in FL, with 1 epoch per round. The open access Pybiscus framework,²⁶ which is built on top of Flower framework,²⁷ and developed in the context of the PAROMA-MED project, was used for all of the experiments.

3.4 Federated learning data distribution setup

To assess the models’ performance, the dataset of both tasks has been divided into training, validation and testing set. For both tasks, the training set comprised approximately 80% of the total dataset. While the validation and testing sets represented two distinct subsets, with approximately 10% each for the CXR classification task, it was necessary to merge them into a single set for the cardiac CT segmentation due to the limited size of the dataset. The same unseen test set was used to evaluate the centralized and the federated experiments.

Figure 1: CXR dataset splits for unbalanced data experiments between (a) 2 clients, (b) 4 clients, and (c) 8 clients.

An initial experiment has been set up in which all the available data was equally distributed among the clients. This one is used to establish baseline results and to make sure the FL configuration works properly.

Experiments have also been conducted with setups involving unbalanced datasets to evaluate the training performance in scenarios close to real-world conditions. For the segmentation task, experiments were performed using a 2-client setup, where the MM-WHS dataset was assigned to the first client and the TS dataset to the second, simulating a scenario where datasets from two distinct centers differ. For the classification task, experiments included setups with 2, 4, and 8 clients, as illustrated in Figure 1. In this context, a *Dirichlet* distribution has been used to simulate non-IID data distribution across clients. Data distribution for the 2-client, 4-client and 8-client setups are respectively presented in Figure 1a, 1b and 1c.

Table 1: Overall classification results of chest X-Ray with balanced and unbalanced data.

Mode	Data conf.	Accuracy	Precision	Sensitivity	
Centralized	–	0.93 (± 0.03)	0.93 (± 0.03)	0.94 (± 0.03)	
Federated	2 clients	Balanced	0.94 (± 0.01)	0.95 (± 0.03)	0.94 (± 0.01)
		Unbalanced	0.93 (± 0.02)	0.94 (± 0.05)	0.94 (± 0.02)
	4 clients	Balanced	0.94 (± 0.04)	0.95 (± 0.03)	0.95 (± 0.04)
		Unbalanced	0.93 (± 0.03)	0.95 (± 0.03)	0.93 (± 0.03)
	8 clients	Balanced	0.93 (± 0.03)	0.94 (± 0.02)	0.94 (± 0.03)
		Unbalanced	0.94 (± 0.03)	0.95 (± 0.02)	0.93 (± 0.03)

4. RESULTS

Concerning CXR classification, accuracy, precision and sensitivity have been computed to assess the overall performance of the model for each setup as shown in table 1. The accuracy was computed globally to provide an overall measure of the model’s performance. Precision and sensitivity were computed using macro averaging, meaning they were first computed for each class individually and then averaged to produce the overall scores. The baseline CL model achieved good overall accuracy, comparable to those obtained in the literature.⁵ The model also achieved high precision and sensitivity of 0.94, indicating its strong ability to identify instances of each class, while minimizing false positive and false negative samples. The results obtained with each of the FL setup models, with both balanced and unbalanced data, remained consistent in terms of accuracy, precision and sensitivity, and closely matched those of the CL model. Figure 2a illustrates the validation loss during the training with balanced data. In this figure, it can be observed that even if the increasing number of clients does

not have a significant impact on the final performance of the model, it does affect the number of rounds it takes for the networks to converge. The loss decrease in each of the experiments shows that the more clients there are in the learning process, the more rounds are needed for convergence.

Figures 2b to 2d depict the loss evolution observed in the experiments with unbalanced data. In the 4-client experiments, both curves exhibit similar shape, with no significant differences in convergence speed between them. However, slight instability can be observed for the training with unbalanced data, indicated by the peaks shown in both 2b and 2c. Additionally, both subfigures show a slightly higher loss value when using an unbalanced dataset.

(a) CL vs. FL with 2, 4, and 8 clients (balanced data).

(b) FL - 2 clients: balanced vs. unbalanced training.

(c) FL - 4 clients: balanced vs. unbalanced training.

(d) FL - 8 clients: balanced vs. unbalanced training.

Figure 2: CXR classification loss decrease comparison between the CL and FL experiments. Subfigures (b), (c), and (d) compare the loss evolution in 2-client, 4-client, and 8-client setups, highlighting the impact of unbalanced data during training.

(a) CL vs. FL with 2 to 16 clients (balanced data).

(b) FL - 2 clients: balanced vs. unbalanced training.

Figure 3: Comparison of CT segmentation loss decrease between CL and FL experiments. Subfigure (b) illustrates the loss evolution in a 2-client setup, with MM-WHS attributed to client 1 and TS to client 2.

To assess the cardiac segmentation performances, we evaluated the predicted segmentations against the labels

Table 2: Segmentation results of cardiac structures obtained with balanced data.

Mode	DSC		HD95 (mm)		
	Myo	LV	Myo	LV	
Centralized	0.88 (± 0.04)	0.93 (± 0.02)	2.61 (± 1.08)	3.08 (± 1.32)	
Federated	2 clients	0.87 (± 0.05)	0.92 (± 0.02)	2.79 (± 1.19)	3.15 (± 1.57)
	4 clients	0.87 (± 0.04)	0.92 (± 0.02)	2.98 (± 1.61)	3.24 (± 1.79)
	8 clients	0.86 (± 0.04)	0.92 (± 0.02)	2.89 (± 0.98)	3.15 (± 1.13)
	16 clients	0.85 (± 0.04)	0.92 (± 0.02)	3.14 (± 0.02)	3.27 (± 0.99)

using the DSC and the 95% Hausdorff distance (HD95). HD95 represents the 95th percentile of the distance distribution to reduce the influence of outliers. The detailed results of each experiment in the segmentation task using balanced data are presented in table 2. Both DSC and HD have been computed on each CT scan and averaged to obtain the overall scores. The baseline CL model showed a good segmentation performance with a DSC of 0.88 for the Myo and 0.93 for the LV, close to the results of the literature.^{8,9} In comparison, the FL results showed DSC values ranging from 0.87 in the 2-client setup to 0.85 in the 16-client setup for Myo, while remaining constant at 0.92 for LV. In addition, the 2-client setup trained on unbalanced data achieved a DSC of 0.84 for Myo and 0.91 for LV, with corresponding HD95 values of 3.21mm for Myo and 3.55mm for LV. Overall, the HD values are relatively low, indicating accurate boundary predictions. Figure 4 shows a cardiac CT image in the axial plane with the segmentation from each experiment overlaid. From the overall visualization, we can see that the segmentation results remain consistent between the CL baseline method and all the client setups for the FL methods. Figure 3a illustrates the validation loss for the segmentation experiments during training. The same finding that applies to the classification task also applies to segmentation: the more clients involved, the slower convergence becomes. However, after a certain number of rounds, all clients tend to converge to approximately the same point.

Figure 4: A cardiac CT scan from the dataset with overlaid Myo and LV labels in subfigure (a), as well as the predicted segmentations from each of the CL and FL experiments in subfigures (b)–(f).

5. DISCUSSION

These results demonstrated consistency between CL and FL on balanced and unbalanced datasets. In classification experiments with balanced data, some slight variations can be observed, but they remain limited as they fall within the standard deviation. Similarly, when considering the experiments with unbalanced data, no significant difference was observed apart from a slight increase in the standard deviation of precision for the 2-client setup. For the segmentation task, the FL models showed consistent results especially in the LV. However, the Myo DSC decreased slightly as the number of clients doubled, meaning that each client has less data available for training. Regarding the loss evolution, we previously mentioned that increasing the number of participating clients slowed the convergence. As the dataset size remained constant, the increasing number of clients resulted in each client receiving less and less data, down to 5 CT scans per client for local training in the 16-client setup. This reduction in the amount of available data per client likely contributed to the slower convergence, as the learning capacity of each client was limited in each round. On the other side, the curves between balanced and unbalanced data experiments exhibited similar behavior and did not significantly differ in terms of convergence speed. The slightly higher loss value shown in 2b and 2c indicates that both models may converge to a sub-optimal point. In this case, a learning rate decay may solve the problem, as suggested by Li et al.¹⁵

Overall, the results are stable across the experiments, both with balanced and unbalanced data. These findings demonstrate the validity of FL when dealing with unbalanced datasets, which is a likely case in real-world scenarios. However, while the results obtained with FL closely match that of CL, the issue of unbalanced data is not the only challenge encountered when training a model using multi-centric data. Our study focuses on using the baseline Federated Averaging (FedAvg) aggregation method, which convergence can be slowed down by heterogeneous data. Furthermore, the disparity in data representation across all participating centers represents a significant challenge in FL, such as label skew, where some clients may have missing labels. Future research should explore the behavior of a FL model when trained under such conditions.

6. CONCLUSION

We evaluated a federated learning approach for the tasks of CXR classification and cardiac CT segmentation. Our results show that federated learning can achieve competitive performance compared to centralized learning in medical image classification and segmentation tasks. Specifically for the classification task using ResNet18, the FL approach yielded comparable results to the CL one. In the segmentation task, the federated 3D U-Net model consistently achieved high DSC for both the myocardium and the left ventricle across the different client setups, closely matching the centralized model’s performance. The primary difference between CL and FL was that as the number of participating clients in the FL architecture increased, the model converged at a slower rate. These findings suggest that federated learning can be a viable alternative to CL, especially in cases where data privacy and decentralization are important.

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